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Impulse Buying of Fashion Products as the Impact of Hedonic Shopping Motivation and Price Discounts During Harbolnas: Case Study on Generation Z Consumers of Several E-Commerce in Bandung City

Rini Handayani¹, Fansuri Munawar²

^{1,2} Faculty of Economic and Business, Widyatama University, Bandung, Indonesia

Correspondence: Rini Handayani, Faculty of Economic and Business, Widyatama University, Bandung, Indonesia. E-mail: rini.handayani@widyatama.ac.id

Abstract

With the transition of the pandemic status in Indonesia to an endemic stage, consumer shopping behaviors have been affected, although online shopping remains predominant. Studies indicate that online shopping can help improve mood during challenging times like these. Harbolnas is a special moment for consumers who enjoy shopping, as every e-commerce platform offers discounts and a variety of attractive promotions. The abundance of promotions subsequently leads to impulsive buying behavior. The purpose of this study is to understand consumer perceptions of hedonic shopping motivations, price discounts, and impulsive purchases among Generation Z consumers during Harbolnas in Bandung, as well as their impacts. This research is descriptive-verified in nature. The unit of analysis comprises several e-commerce platforms (Tokopedia, Shopee, Bukalapak, Lazada, and Blibli). The observation unit is Generation Z consumers in Bandung who enjoy online shopping. The minimum sample size is 100 individuals. Data collection techniques include questionnaires and interviews, while the sampling technique employed is purposive sampling. The analytical tool used is multiple linear regression. Hypothesis testing indicates that hedonic shopping motivations and price discounts significantly influence impulsive buying behavior among Generation Z consumers in Bandung.

Keywords: Hedonic Shopping Motivation, Price Discount, Impulse Purchase, E-Commerce, Harbolnas

1. Introduction

According to the We Are Social report, the number of internet users in Indonesia reached 213 million by January 2023. This figure represents 77% of Indonesia's total population of 276.4 million at the beginning of 2023. The number of internet users in the country increased by 5.44% year-on-year (Liu et al., 2018). Online shopping through e-commerce has become a societal habit, primarily driven by the COVID-19 pandemic. This trend is evident in the e-economy SEA 2023 report, which states that 80% of internet users in Indonesia have shopped online at least once (katadata.co.id, September 2023). Some of the reasons consumers choose to shop online include the ability to access catalogs and goods for sale 24 hours a day without time restrictions, the ease of

comparing prices from different shops, saving time and money, and the extensive range of available products (both domestic and international). The momentum of the pandemic has necessitated the transfer of almost all basic needs and various other activities to digital services, including shopping via e-commerce (Galhotra & Dewan, 2020).

The survey results indicate that the majority (91%) of the public have shopped during promotional campaigns on online shopping platforms, such as twin dates, Harbolnas, and Pay Day (Putri & Rohman, 2018). Additionally, 67% of respondents expressed high enthusiasm for promotional campaigns due to benefits such as additional free shipping (75%), flash sales (69%), and double discounts (60%). According to the Populix survey, 54% of Indonesians prefer to shop on e-commerce platforms, with the majority being Generation Z. Generation Z, defined as those born between 1995 and 2010, generally exhibit a fear of missing out (FOMO) when shopping, largely due to their exposure to social media interactions (Karimkhan & Chapa, 2021). Consequently, Gen Z tends to purchase goods or products impulsively, following current lifestyle trends. The numerous promotions offered often lead to impulse buying, characterized by an impulsive or sudden decision to purchase goods or services without prior planning (Yadav & Sharma, 2022). The Trade Desk found that Indonesian consumers can be categorized into two types when it comes to online shopping: planned shoppers and impulsive shoppers. Approximately 64% are planned shoppers, while 14% identify as impulsive. Interestingly, during online shopping festivals, about 42% of consumers who consider themselves planned shoppers become impulsive, leading to an increase in the number of products they purchase (Akram et al., 2018). This phenomenon is evidenced by the doubling of impulse purchases during online shopping festivals.

The frequently purchased product categories are food and drink (69%), household goods (68%), fashion (59%), fresh food (41%), personal care (48%), and cosmetics (39%). Fashion, in particular, remains a significant product category amidst the development of an increasingly modern industry. Fashion choices can reflect and express a person's identity and social status, making individuals easily identifiable by their attire. Involvement in fashion is closely linked to personal characteristics, especially among women and the younger generation. A high level of involvement in fashion facilitates impulse purchases of fashion products, as consumers desire to appear fashionable and attractive (Kautish & Sharma, 2018). A survey of 2,000 people in the US, conducted by both Slickdeals and OnePoll, found that the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted spending habits. Interestingly, the research also indicates that online shopping can help improve people's spirits during challenging times like the current pandemic (Sheth, 2020). According to the survey results, 72% of respondents admitted to making impulse purchases online during the pandemic. They also reported experiencing a positive impact on their mood due to online shopping during the lockdown period (Gupta & Mukherjee, 2022).

Hedonic shopping motives are prevalent among many teenagers today due to environmental influences. This is especially true for Generation Z, those born between 1995 and 2010, who were exposed to technology earlier than previous generations. The primary reason Generation Z shops online is to save time and money. This generation values information, aesthetics, ease of use, security, and privacy when using a website (Elida et al., 2023; Priporas et al., 2017). With a marketing strategy that employs attractive promotions and significant discounts, consumers, especially Generation Z, purchase goods they do not need because they feel happy and satisfied when acquiring products at low prices (Pika, 2023). One factor influencing impulse purchases is price discounts, which are reductions from the list price set by companies during a specific period to attract more consumers to buy a product (Ajizah & Nugroho, 2023). Another important factor influencing impulse buying is hedonic shopping motivation. Hedonic shopping behavior involves activities aimed at seeking pleasure and satisfaction (Widagdo & Roz, 2021). This view is supported by the research of Octaviana & Komariah (2022), who found that hedonic shopping motivation and price discounts influence impulse purchases. However, according to the research by Ittaqullah et al. (2020) and Purnamasari et al. (2021), hedonic shopping motivation and price discounts have no effect on impulse purchases.

Impulsive buying is difficult to avoid during massive, short-term discounts such as Harbolnas. Research has shown that impulse buying is more likely to involve items that are not truly needed or are needed less (Shi & Joo, 2023). Customers are not only tempted by price cuts but are also unable to think rationally due to the deliberately short duration for decision-making (Putri & Rohman, 2018). The number of promotions and

discounts offered by each e-commerce platform leads to impulse buying behavior, characterized by an impulsive or sudden decision to purchase goods or services without prior planning (Panjaitan & Marpaung, 2023). Impulse purchases are spontaneous decisions made by consumers when they see promotions on the web and can be triggered by various factors, such as attractive products, discounts, or new arrivals. Consumers are particularly motivated to purchase products when they are offered at low prices and discounts (Ahmetoglu et al., 2014). According to Bhakat & Muruganatham (2013) research, external and internal factors can stimulate impulsive buying. Among the external factors, price discounts are one of the primary stimuli. Internally, there is the hedonic motivational factor, which is related to feelings that are more dominant than rational thinking when shopping. The research results of Xu & Huang (2014), Noor et al. (2020), and Widyastuti & Hariasih (2023) indicate that hedonic shopping motivation and price discounts trigger impulse buying. The findings of Octaviana & Komariah (2022) further suggest that better price discounts and increasing hedonic shopping motivation correlate with higher levels of impulse purchases, and vice versa.

Therefore, due to the gap in previous research, the researchers are interested in understanding the effect of hedonic shopping motivation and price discounts on impulse purchases. The purpose of this study is to determine the impact of hedonic shopping motivation, price discounts, and impulse purchases on Generation Z consumers during Harbolnas in Bandung.

2. Method

This research is descriptive and verification-based. The unit of analysis comprises several e-commerce platforms in the city of Bandung, including Tokopedia, Shopee, Bukalapak, Lazada, and Blibli. These e-commerce platforms were chosen based on their popularity and high visitation rates in Bandung. The sampling technique employed is purposive sampling. The observation unit consists of Generation Z consumers who enjoy online shopping during Harbolnas in Bandung. The minimum sample size is 100 individuals. Data collection techniques include online questionnaires and interviews. The analytical tool used is multiple linear regression (Ofosu-Boateng, 2020).

Figure 1: Research model

3. Results

The validity test for all the variable questions studied indicates that the rhit value of each question item is $\geq$ table 0.165, confirming their validity. For the dimension of hedonic shopping motivation, Cronbach's alpha is 0.763; for price discounts, Cronbach's alpha is 0.745; and for impulse purchases, Cronbach's alpha is 0.747. This means that all variable questions studied are reliable, as Cronbach's alpha $>$ 0.70 (Ghozali, 2020).

3.1 Descriptive evaluation

Descriptive analysis through frequency distribution can provide relative and cumulative information about the object of research. Interviewees' responses on hedonic shopping motives (X1), discounts (X2), and impulsive buying (Y).

Table 1: Interviewees' responses

No.	Statements	%	Description
	Hedonic Shopping Motivation		
1	I plan to purchase products during Harbolnas because the discounts offered are appealing	40	Agree
2	I will purchase products offered during Harbolnas, as the prices are very reasonable.	45	Agree
3	I will purchase products during Harbolnas, as the discounts offered are substantial within a short period.	50	Agree
	Price Discount		
1	I plan to purchase products during Harbolnas because the discounts offered are attractive	40	Agree
2	I will purchase products offered during Harbolnas, as the prices are very reasonable	45	Agree
3	I will purchase products during Harbolnas, as the discounts offered are substantial within a short period.	50	Agree
	Impulse Buying		
1	I tend to buy in bulk during Harbolnas when there is a special offer.	49	Agree
2	During Harbolnas, I tend to shop impulsively.	45	Fairly
3	I tend to be obsessed with spending my money on products offered during Harbolnas.	43	Fairly
4	I tend to buy products during Harbolnas that I don't really need.	43	Agree

From the descriptive analysis, it is evident that online shopping can increase the hedonic shopping motivation of consumers in Bandung. This is reflected in the respondents' rankings, which indicate agreement that online shopping can arouse consumers' curiosity and interest in fashion products and make shopping an exciting activity. Online shopping can improve consumers' mood and alleviate boredom. Consequently, consumers will always make time to shop online to keep up with the latest trends and fashions with friends or family.

Respondents' answers indicate that discounts during Harbolnas can encourage consumers to make purchases. This is evident from the ranking of respondents' answers, which shows agreement that price discounts during Harbolnas can motivate consumers to buy products. Consumers perceive that the discounts offered during Harbolnas are substantial within a short period, the prices are very low, and the discount programs are attractive.

Respondents' answers indicate that Harbolnas can encourage impulse buying among Bandung consumers. This is evident from the ranking of respondents' answers, which show agreement with shopping in large quantities during special offers and purchasing products even when they are not really needed. However, consumers generally shop with sufficient forethought and are not overly obsessed with spending their money during Harbolnas.

3.2 Analysis of Multiple Linear Regression

The results of data processing based on SPSS calculations yielded the following multiple regression equations:

Table 2: Multiple Linear Regression Test Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficient	t	Sig
	B	Std. error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	2.956	2.707		1.091	.277
Hedonis Shopping Motivation	.498	.095	.479	5.172	.000
Price Discount	.587	.245	.221	2.387	.018

a. Dependent Variable: Impulsive Buying

Source: SPSS data processing results, 2024

From the above table, the following regression equation can be derived:

$$Y = 2,956 + 0,498 X_1 + 0,587 X_2 + e$$

The constant of 2.956 indicates that in the absence of hedonic purchase motivation and price discounts, impulse purchases will be 2.956. If hedonic shopping motivation increases by 1 unit, while other variables remain constant, impulse purchases will increase by 0.498 units. Similarly, if the price discount increases by 1 unit, while other variables remain constant, impulse purchases will increase by 0.587 units.

3.3 Simultaneous Hypothesis Test (F-test)

The F-test is used to determine the significance level of the combined (simultaneous) influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. After testing the hypothesis simultaneously, the following results were obtained based on the data processing performed:

Table 3: Hypothesis testing by F-test (F-test) ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig
1 Regression	615.684	2	307.842	31.002	.000
Residual	963.154	97	9.928		
Total	1578,839	99			

a. Dependent Variable: Impulsive Buying

b. Predictors: (Constant), Hedonic Shopping Motivation, Price Discount

Source: SPSS data processing results, 2024

From the table above, it can be seen that the value of $F_{\text{calculated}}$ (31.002) is greater than F_{table} (1.34). Therefore, H_0 is rejected and H_{ais} is accepted, indicating that there is a significant simultaneous influence of hedonic shopping motivation and price discounts on impulse purchases of Generation Z consumers during Harbolnas in Bandung City.

The magnitude of the correlation and the influence of hedonic shopping motivation and price discounts on impulse buying are presented in the following table:

Table 4: Determination Coefficient (R^2) Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
.1	.623 ^a	.389	.376	3.150

a. Dependent Variable: Impulsive Buying

b. Predictors: (Constant), Hedonic Shopping Motivation, Price Discount

Based on Table 4, the result of the calculation of the multiple correlation coefficient (R) is 0.623. This value is in the interval 0.600 - 0.799, which means that Hedonic Shopping Motivation and Price Discounts have a fairly strong relationship with Impulse Purchases. The coefficient of determination is 0.389 or 38.9%, which means that Hedonic Shopping Motivation and Price Discounts have an influence of 38.9% on repurchase interest.

4. Discussion

From the descriptive analysis of hedonic shopping motivation, it is evident that online shopping can increase the hedonic shopping motivation of consumers in Bandung. This insight can be valuable for e-commerce entrepreneurs, highlighting the importance of satisfying consumers' needs for self-satisfaction, pleasure, fantasy, social interaction, and emotional fulfillment. Respondents' answers about discounts indicate that the discounts

offered during Harbolnas are generally well-received, although the attractiveness of the discounts received the lowest score. To address this, e-commerce platforms could create more appealing discount programs, such as offering bundling packages by combining several products at a low price (e.g., pairing a best-selling product with a less popular but related product like shoes and socks), special discounts for the first 10 buyers or free shipping, buy one get one free promotions, flash sales with very low prices for a short period (1-2 hours), and cash back discounts limited to a percentage or amount that can be used on subsequent transactions. Additionally, e-commerce platforms could use a variety of unique and different promotional concepts, such as offering discounts based on names or birthdays, or creating interesting promotions using creative videos or unique photos and illustrations.

From the respondents' answers about impulse purchases, it is evident that impulse purchases among consumers in Bandung city during Harbolnas are quite high, with the lowest score for the obsession to spend money during this event. This indicates that many consumers are now more careful and thorough when shopping, realizing that sometimes discounted products do not meet their expectations and that the discounted price may actually be the same as the original price, as some e-commerce platforms increase the product price before applying the discount. Therefore, it is crucial for e-commerce platforms to provide accurate and honest information to consumers when advertising and setting the selling price of discounted products. Statistical test results show that hedonic purchase motivation and discounts significantly affect impulse purchases, consistent with research by Bhakat & Muruganatham (2013), Noor et al. (2020), Octaviana & Komariah (2022), and Shi & Joo (2023), which state that hedonic shopping motivation and price discounts trigger impulse purchases, where better price discounts and increasing hedonic shopping motivation lead to higher impulse purchases.

5. Conclusion

Based on the research carried out by the author through statistical data analysis of distributed questionnaires and interviews, the following conclusions can be drawn: First, the descriptive analysis of hedonic shopping motivation reveals that online shopping can enhance the hedonic shopping motivation of consumers in Bandung, as indicated by respondents' agreement that online shopping stimulates their curiosity and interest in fashion products, making shopping an exciting activity. Online shopping also improves consumers' mood and alleviates boredom, prompting them to regularly shop online to keep up with the latest trends and fashions with friends or family. Second, respondents' answers regarding price discounts show that the discounts offered by e-commerce during Harbolnas are generally well-received, although the attractiveness of the discounts scored the lowest. Third, respondents' answers about impulse buying indicate that impulse buying in Bandung city during Harbolnas is quite high, with the lowest score for the obsession to spend money. Statistical test results show that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, indicating that hedonic shopping motivation and price discounts have a 38.9% influence on impulse buying among Generation Z consumers in Bandung during Harbolnas.

Researchers propose the following suggestions as input for e-commerce entrepreneurs in the city of Bandung: First, e-commerce entrepreneurs should pay more attention to and strive to meet consumers' needs for self-satisfaction, pleasure, fantasy, and social and emotional fulfillment. Second, e-commerce platforms should design more attractive discount programs, such as offering bundled packages, special discounts, buy-one-get-one-free promotions, flash sales, cash back, and unique and different promotions like name or birthday discounts, as well as creating engaging promotional advertisements with creative videos or unique illustrations. Third, e-commerce platforms must provide accurate and honest information to consumers when advertising and setting the selling price of discounted products, ensuring that consumers are more inclined to spend their money during Harbolnas.

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